

STUDY OF SEED MOVEMENT

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Abstract. In the article, the speed of movement of seeds along the projection of the axes along the surface of the seeding device, the analytical connections for determining the absolute speed, as well as the expressions for calculating the laws of movement along the seed nest of the reel in the coordinate axes are presented.

Keywords: seed movement, F_{ishq} -friction force, G -gravity force, P -reaction force and F_e -inertia force in seed movement, displacement of seed on the reel in the projection of coordinate axes and absolute speed as a function of time, angular acceleration.

The main part: Movement of seeds in the coil are fully described in their scientific works of Vasilenko P.M, Shevchenko I.A, Gevko B. M, Kirova A. A, Manchev A. V, Radugina N. P, Sisolina P. V and others.

In the study of seed movement, it can be seen in Figure 1 that the following forces act at point O: F_{ishq} -friction force, G -weight force, P -reaction force and F_e -inertia force in seed movement. The seed falls from the reel under the influence of gravity. Here is the force of gravity $G = mg$ (1) is determined by the expression.

Here: m - seed weight, kg;

g -is the speed of free fall, m/c^2

The coefficient of friction affecting the movement of the seed is determined when the force F_{max} that moves it reaches its maximum value. It tries to balance the movement of the seed with the force of friction ($f \cdot G \cdot \sin \varphi$).

Figure 1. Scheme of the location of the seed relative to the side walls of the coil and the forces acting at point O

Since the seed falls from the hopper to the roller under the slope, the initial velocity V_0 of the seed can be considered equal to 0.

When determining the movement of the seed, the following points can be taken into account:

1. When the seed is moving, the air resistance forces are not taken into account, because it is smaller than the friction force during movement along the inclined plane and compared to the speed of the seed movement.

2. The mass of the seed is concentrated in its center of gravity [1; 44-b].

Methodology: When the reel reaches its maximum angular acceleration, the seed falls from the slot. The seed falling on the reel is acted upon by a centrifugal force $F_m = m\omega^2 r$ and a frictional force $F_{ishq} = fmg$ opposite to it. When the above forces are balanced, the seed will drop from the reel seat.

$$F_m = F_{ishq} \text{ or } m\omega^2 R = fmg \quad (2)$$

If the friction angle β , formed due to mutual contact of the seeds, is variable, then the speed of seed's descent depends on its contact surface with the roller wall. Therefore, if $\beta = 0$, seed's falling speed is also equal to $V_{or} = 0$ at this point on the reel.

The inertial force when the seed reaches point O will be equal to

$$F_n = m\bar{a} = m\omega^2 R$$

where: ω - is the angular speed of the coil rotation, rad/s
 R – coil radius, mm.

It can be seen from Figure 1 that the frictional force generated by the movement of the seed on the surface of the reel is directed in the opposite direction to the speed of the reel. The normal force $F_{uuk} \cdot \cos\varphi$ causes the reaction force N acting on the seed. Based on these considerations, the following expression can be written to determine the normal force

$$N = F_{uuk} \cos\varphi \quad (3)$$

The friction force prevents the seed in contact with the surface of the reel from sliding [3].

$$F_{uuk} = f \cdot G_1 = f \cdot m \cdot g \cdot \sin\varphi \quad (4)$$

where: $G_1 - G$ component of gravity, H

φ – deviation angle, grad.

G – the force of gravity acting on the seed, H

m - seed weight, kg

f - coefficient of friction.

Therefore, in order for the seed to move when it is in contact with the surface of the reel, the following equation must be fulfilled [4].

$$F_{uuk} \cdot \cos\varphi > f \cdot G_1 \quad (5)$$

When analyzing seed movement (Fig. 1), the following conditions should be taken into account.

1. After the seed leaves the nest, V_e force F_{uuk} is generated due to its weight m , which is opposite to the speed a .

2. A movement of mg occurs when the seed falls off the reel [5].

Taking into account the above, we write the main equation of the movement of the seed with respect to the axis n normal [1; 45-b]

$$m \frac{d^2 n}{d\tau} = \sum F_{xi} \quad (6)$$

In this: $\sum F_{xi}$ - sum of active forces affecting the seed, H

It can be seen from Fig. 1 that the forces acting on seed $\sum F_{xi}$ can be written as follows [6]:

$$\sum F_{xi} = F_n + G = F_\tau + F_{ishq} \quad (7)$$

The seed starts moving at point M, and at this point the reaction force N is equal to 0. The force F_τ acting on the movement of the seed is assumed to be proportional to the speed:

$$F_\tau = f \cdot mV$$

At point O, we write the equations of motion relative to the projection of the forces acting on the seed in the normal coordinate systems τ and n :

$$m\ddot{n} = F_\tau \sin \varphi + F_n \quad (8)$$

$$m\ddot{\tau} = -G + F_{ishq} \cos \varphi \quad (9)$$

Taking into account expressions (3) and (4), expressions (8) and (9) can be written as follows:

$$m\ddot{n} = f \cdot m \cdot V_n \sin \varphi + m\omega^2 R \quad (10)$$

$$m\ddot{\tau} = mg + f \cdot m \cdot g \cdot \sin \varphi \quad (11)$$

(11) we take conditions $t = 0, V_x = 0,$ and $x = 0$ as initial conditions for the expression and then integrate the expression

$$m \frac{dv_n}{dt} = -f \cdot m \cdot V_n \sin \varphi + m\omega^2 R \quad (12)$$

(12) reduce both sides of the equation to m and make it look like this:

$$\frac{dv_n}{dt} = -f \cdot V_n \sin \varphi + \omega^2 R \quad (13)$$

After separating the variables, we get the following view:

$$\frac{dv_n}{-f \cdot V_n \cdot \sin \varphi + \omega^2 R} = dt \quad (14)$$

We integrate equation (14) with speed up to $V_0 = 0$ and t up to $t_0 = 0$.

$$\int_0^{V_n} \frac{dv_n}{\omega^2 \cdot R - f \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot V_n} = \int_0^t dt \quad (15)$$

After integration, we get the following equation:

$$-\frac{1}{f \cdot \sin \varphi} \cdot \ln(\omega^2 R - f \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot V_n) = t + C_1 \quad (16)$$

From this : C_1 – constant integrator.

$$C_1 = \frac{1}{-f \cdot \sin \varphi} \cdot \ln \omega^2 R$$

Then we can write equation (16) as follows:

$$-\frac{1}{f \cdot \sin \varphi} \cdot \ln(\omega^2 R - f \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot V_n) + \frac{1}{f \cdot \sin \varphi} \ln \omega^2 R = t \quad (17)$$

(17) as a result of mathematical changes, we make the expression look like this:

$$\ln\left(\frac{\omega^2 R - f \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot V_n}{\omega^2 R}\right) = -t \cdot f \cdot \sin \varphi \quad (18)$$

$\ln x = 2; x = e^2$ using the fact that is equal to , the expression (18) can be written as follows:

$$\omega^2 R - f \cdot \sin \varphi \cdot V_n = \omega^2 R \cdot e^{-t \cdot f \cdot \sin \varphi} \quad (19)$$

After mathematical transformations of the expression (19), we determine the speed of

movement of the seed on the reel V_n for the projection on the axis τ

$$V_n = \frac{\omega^2 R(1 - e^{-t \cdot f \cdot \sin \varphi})}{f \cdot \sin \varphi} \quad (20)$$

To determine the displacement of the seed in the projection on the τ axis, we replace the

expression (20) with the variable $V_n = \frac{dS_n}{dt}$. Then we get the following expression:

$$\frac{dS_n}{dt} = \frac{\omega^2 R(1 - e^{-t \cdot f \cdot \sin \varphi})}{f \cdot \sin \varphi} \quad (21)$$

We integrate the expression (21):

$$\int dS = \int \frac{\omega^2 R(1 - e^{-t \cdot f \cdot \sin \varphi})}{f \cdot \sin \varphi} dt \quad (22)$$

After integration, expression (22) becomes:

$$S_n = \int \frac{\omega^2 R(1 - e^{-t \cdot f \cdot \sin \varphi})}{f \cdot \sin \varphi} dt$$

$$S_n = \frac{\omega^2 R(1 - e^{-t \cdot f \cdot \sin \varphi})}{f \cdot \sin \varphi} \cdot t + c_3 \quad (23)$$

C_3 - constant of integration is found by expression (23) based on initial conditions. It will be equal to $C_3 = 0$. The equation then becomes:

$$S_n = \frac{\omega^2 R(1 - e^{-t \cdot f \cdot \sin \varphi})}{f \cdot \sin \varphi} \cdot t \quad (24)$$

(24) we give the final expression based on initial conditions: $t = 0$, $S_n = 0$, $V_\tau = 0$ of the equation of motion relative to the projection of the forces acting on the seed onto the τ axis of the vector expression as follows [3; 48-51-b]:

$$V_\tau = g(\sin \varphi - f)t \quad (25)$$

Here: V_τ - the speed of the reel on the projection of the seed on the τ axis, m/c .

The speed of movement of the seed on the reel is equal to the sum of the speeds of its projections on the coordinate axes

$$V = \sqrt{V_\tau^2 + V_n^2} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\omega^2 R(1 - e^{-t \cdot f \cdot \sin \varphi})}{f \cdot \sin \varphi}\right)^2 + (g(\sin \varphi - f)t)^2} \quad (26)$$

Result: To determine the speed of movement of seeds along the surface of the roller of the sowing device along the projection of the n normal and τ axes and the displacement of the seed on the roller in the projections of the coordinate axes, we calculate the numerical solutions using the Microsoft Excel program. We perform calculations on the values in the $\omega = 6,14 \text{ rad/c}$; $\varphi = [0 \dots 0,86]$; $t \in [0; 0,5]$; $V_0 [0; 1,25]$; $g = 9,8 \text{ m/c}^2$ interval and build the graph shown in Figure 2 based on the obtained results.

From the graph in Figure 2, the movement of the seed in the axes of normal coordinates n moves 0.01 m in 0.1 s, 0.04 m in 0.2 s, and 0.1 m in 0.3 s.

From the graph in Figure 3, the absolute speed of the seed in motion is 7.3 m/s when the spool is 0.1 s, 4.5 m/s at 0.3 s, and 4.3 m/s at 0.5 s.

Figure 2. The graph of the time dependence of the displacement of the seed on the reel in the projection of the coordinate axes

Figure 3. Time dependence graph of the absolute speed of the seed falling into the slot of the reel in the coordinate axes

Conclusion: Based on the above, it can be said that the speed of movement of seeds along the surface of the roller of the sowing device along the normal and axis projection (25), analytical connections for determining the absolute speed (26), as well as the expressions (24) for calculating the laws of movement along the seed nest of the roller received.

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